

IN-SITU COMPACTION ON PEAT ALTERS WATER TABLE DEPTH IN CONTROLLING CARBON EMISSIONS

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INTRODUCTION

A new technique introduced recently during land opening practices for oil palm establishment on tropical peatland refers to peat compaction. While in the early stage of land preparation, peat compaction occurs naturally by oxidation of peat materials during drainage, this approach seeks to actively increase compaction by additional mechanical exertion with the intention of increasing peat bulk density to a minimum of 0.20 g cm⁻³. Compaction practice on soil affects its integrity by causing forced deformation on the macro structure of the soil. This condition causes reconfiguration of soil pores, reduction in soil volume, restriction on the available oxygen, decreased water infiltration, and increased water content (Novara et al., 2012; Yahya et al., 2011). Kuncoro et al. (2014) asserted that the deformation of physical structures in compacted soils could affect air and water transportation in various ways, depending on the connectivity of macro pores. As such, drained tropical peatland under agriculture is susceptible to carbon depletion due to peat oxidation and deposition alteration to soil moisture, bulk density, and soil pore size, and other factors associated with compaction. Compaction has the potential to change the extent and signature of GHG gas emissions throughout time and space, as well as the levels of oxidation alteration. While some studies have investigated the effects of soil compaction on carbon emissions and soil-water, experimental data related to tropical peat soil-induced compaction on physicochemical properties and carbon emissions is rare. Therefore, this study aims to assess the effect of compaction effort on the peat physicochemical properties and carbon emissions.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study location

The study was conducted in two tropical peatlands in the state of Selangor, Malaysia; a drained and logged-over peat swamp forest (SF) in Tanjung Karang (3°41'49.2" N 101°11'06.0" E) and a 10-year-old, 2nd generation oil palm plantation (OP), Sepang (2°44'20.4" N 101°39'10.8" E). The peat depth at SF and OP was between 165.4 ± 3.9 (SD) cm, and 95.2 ± 6.5 (SD) cm, considered moderate depth. According to USDA soil taxonomy, the peat soils in both areas can be classified as Typic Fibric Tropohemist.

Fabrication of hybrid compaction apparatus

The compaction apparatus was fabricated using stainless steel based on a vertical plunger-like compression. A soil collar cylinder measuring 40.0 cm long with a diameter of 10.16 cm, was used to standardise compaction magnitudes and maintain compaction degree due to the peat's high plasticity and recovery features. A piston measuring 30.0 cm high, and 10.16 cm diameter were used to compress the peat surface to the assigned soil depth. The piston also served as a static closed chamber for capturing gas.

Compaction using fabricated compaction apparatus

The soil collars were then driven into the peat profile and left for two months to allow resettlement and the root necrosis and exclusion of root biomass which would otherwise contribute to additional autotrophic emissions. Together, the compaction treatments were assigned as Ref (reference for control or no compaction without soil collar); T0 (no compaction with soil collar); T10 (soil compression treatment to 10.0 cm); T20 (20.0 cm); and T30 (30.0 cm), as per Figure 1.

Figure 1 Schematic of peat compaction apparatus installation at the peat swamp forest (SF) and the oil palm plantation (OP).

Gas sampling, analysis, and water table measurement

Gas carbon emissions were measured using automated gas analyser (Ultraportable gas analyser by Los Gatos Research, USA). Mixed gas accumulation was analysed in a real time for six minutes and each of gas concentration points represented 20 seconds, which was recorded and stored automatically in the analyser's data logger. The gas concentration in ppm was calculated using ideal gas law. During gas sampling, all water table depth were retrieved from three perforated piezometers and the average measurements calculated.

Peat sampling and physicochemical properties analysis

The peat and bulk density samples were collected separately from the soil collars at the end of the compaction experiment. Dry bulk density (BD) and moisture content parameters were analysed by adhering to the methods prescribed by Al-Shammary et al. (2018). Loss on ignition was determined from a small fraction of composite oven-dried peat (5.0 g) via complete combustion. Following the method suggested by Blake (1958), the value of particle density can be obtained using pycnometer or specific gravity flask. The peat pH value was determined by using a benchtop pH meter model (Sartorius pHBasic, Germany). The total carbon, total nitrogen, hydrogen, sulphur, and CN ratio were determined following the standard method of elemental analysis in accordance with ISO 13878:1998 using a Vario MACRO cube CHNS analyser (Elementary analysis system, Germany).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The change in physicochemical properties of the surface peat samples because of compaction treatments is shown in Table 1. Importantly, despite the compression by depth of the compaction apparatus, there was not a clear relationship between treatment and BD and no significant difference across treatments within each area. As compaction treatments lowered the soil surface compared to surrounding areas, there was a change in relative water table depth compared to the modified surface level, resulting in the expected significant difference in water table heights between treatments for both ecosystems. The lack of response of peat properties to the compaction treatments was unexpected and suggested that at the forces applied here at least, the peat in both ecosystems was resilient towards artificial compaction. This effect results from water table fluctuation interaction, especially at maximum compaction, T30 (−30.0 cm compression), where the modified soil surface level was closest to the water table level. The water table level at maximum compaction during the study of SF and OP fluctuated from -6.26 ± 7.35 (SD) cm and -26.8 ± 8.59 (SD) cm, when compaction went above −30.0 cm. Water table level interference was also observed by Baker et al. (2004) who suggested that water table level fluctuation in wetting and drying cycles could cause looseness or impaired pore structure or swelling of soils.

Table 1 Physicochemical properties of the compaction treatments (mean \pm standard error, n= 4) between the two ecosystems. The difference in the uppercase (between ecosystems) and lowercase (interaction effects) letters in bold in the same column indicates significant differences at $p \leq 0.05$.

		Physical property					
Ecosystem	Treatment	Bulk density (g cm ⁻³)	Loss on ignition (%)	Total porosity (%)	Water-filled pore space (%)	Gravimetric water content (%)	Volumetric water content (%)
Secondary Peat swamp forest (SF)	T0	0.15 ^a \pm 0.03	72.8 ^a \pm 9.9	91.5 ^a \pm 1.2	34.2 ^a \pm 5.9	214.9 ^a \pm 22.7	31.1 ^a \pm 4.9
	T10	0.19 ^a \pm 0.02	79.0 ^a \pm 10.2	86.4 ^a \pm 0.5	45.1 ^a \pm 1.9	214.0 ^a \pm 27.7	39.9 ^a \pm 1.9
	T20	0.15 ^a \pm 0.02	85.7 ^a \pm 3.8	90.7 ^a \pm 0.8	41.5 ^a \pm 2.4	257.8 ^a \pm 23.4	37.6 ^a \pm 2.1
	T30	0.19 ^a \pm 0.03	85.1 ^a \pm 1.9	88.2 ^a \pm 2.2	42.9 ^a \pm 7.1	214.5 ^a \pm 37.7	37.6 ^a \pm 5.7
	Mean	0.17^B \pm 0.01	80.7 ^A \pm 3.6	89.7^A \pm 0.7	40.9 ^A \pm 2.4	225.3^A \pm 13.6	36.5 ^A \pm 2.0
Oil palm plantation (OP)	T0	0.18 ^a \pm 0.02	85.9 ^a \pm 1.3	88.6 ^a \pm 1.3	38.7 ^a \pm 3.1	195.4 ^a \pm 23.7	34.2 ^a \pm 2.7
	T10	0.22 ^a \pm 0.04	83.8 ^a \pm 0.6	86.4 ^a \pm 2.4	40.0 ^a \pm 5.7	163.7 ^a \pm 15.7	34.2 ^a \pm 4.2
	T20	0.28 ^a \pm 0.06	81.9 ^a \pm 1.1	83.2 ^a \pm 3.8	47.7 ^a \pm 4.7	161.7 ^a \pm 29.2	39.2 ^a \pm 2.1
	T30	0.25 ^a \pm 0.01	85.5 ^a \pm 2.3	84.0 ^a \pm 1.2	54.5 ^a \pm 7.0	180.5 ^a \pm 25.3	45.7 ^a \pm 5.8
	Mean	0.23^A \pm 0.02	84.3 ^A \pm 0.8	85.5^B \pm 1.2	45.2 ^A \pm 2.9	175.3^B \pm 11.3	38.3 ^A \pm 2.1
		Chemical property					
Ecosystem	Treatment	pH value (1:2.5) (Peat:water)	Total carbon (%)	Total Nitrogen (%)	Hydrogen (%)	Sulphur (%)	C:N ratio (%)
Secondary peat swamp forest (SF)	T0	3.06 ^a \pm 0.02	33.9 ^a \pm 4.5	1.6 ^a \pm 0.3	4.7 ^a \pm 0.9	7.0 ^a \pm 3.7	22.5 ^a \pm 1.8
	T10	3.04 ^a \pm 0.04	36.1 ^a \pm 4.7	1.4 ^a \pm 0.2	5.6 ^a \pm 1.0	3.7 ^a \pm 2.2	26.6 ^a \pm 2.7
	T20	3.01 ^a \pm 0.03	41.4 ^a \pm 2.2	1.6 ^a \pm 0.2	6.5 ^a \pm 0.8	2.5 ^a \pm 1.0	26.9 ^a \pm 3.2
	T30	3.07 ^a \pm 0.03	38.0 ^a \pm 2.1	1.6 ^a \pm 0.1	6.0 ^a \pm 0.7	3.8 ^a \pm 1.0	25.0 ^a \pm 1.7
	Mean	3.05 ^A \pm 0.01	37.4^B \pm 1.8	1.5 ^A \pm 0.1	5.7^B \pm 0.4	4.3^A \pm 1.2	25.2^B \pm 1.2
Oil palm plantation (OP)	T0	2.89 ^a \pm 0.1	43.2 ^a \pm 1.1	1.4 ^a \pm 0.0	14.2 ^a \pm 1.1	0.4 ^a \pm 0.9	31.7 ^a \pm 0.9
	T10	2.92 ^a \pm 0.1	41.9 ^a \pm 1.6	1.3 ^a \pm 0.1	13.9 ^a \pm 0.43	0.4 ^a \pm 0.1	32.2 ^a \pm 1.5
	T20	3.01 ^a \pm 0.1	42.9 ^a \pm 1.8	1.4 ^a \pm 0.1	13.1 ^a \pm 0.7	0.5 ^a \pm 0.1	29.6 ^a \pm 0.8
	T30	3.18 ^a \pm 0.2	42.4 ^a \pm 2.3	1.37 ^a \pm 0.1	13.9 ^a \pm 2.0	0.5 ^a \pm 0.2	31.2 ^a \pm 1.2
	Mean	3.00 ^A \pm 0.1	42.5^A \pm 0.8	1.37 ^A \pm 0.0	13.8^A \pm 0.6	0.44^B \pm 0.1	31.16^A \pm 0.6

Despite physicochemical properties being unaffected by site-specific artificial compaction, CO₂ and CH₄ from the peat surface carbon emissions showed inverse patterns due to compaction, especially in the SF ecosystem. During compaction, CO₂ emissions decreased according to the treatment, with the greatest reduction measured at T30, by 827.2 mg CO₂ m⁻² hr⁻¹ (64%), followed by 465.1 mg CO₂ m⁻² hr⁻¹ (36%) at T20 with an average of 50%. Contrary to CO₂, CH₄ emission showed a significant increase in T20 and T30 treatments by 42.2 μ g CH₄ m⁻² hr⁻¹

¹ (85%) and 109.6 $\mu\text{g CH}_4 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ hr}^{-1}$ (224%), respectively, within the SF ecosystem. Our results found uncompacted (T0) SF to be a substantial sink for CH_4 and OP T0 to be a weak CH_4 sink. This may have been due to a higher labile C surface peat content, a source of substrate that has a CH_4 production priming effect (Girkin et al., 2018) as compared to our matured OP. Given that there was no change in the physiochemical variables with treatments, the only significant difference between treatments was not the compaction/BD, but rather the increase in relative water table depth (Figure 2).

Figure 2 Relationship between water table level and (a) CO_2 and (b) CH_4 emissions at SF ($n = 29-32$). The point within the solid circle indicates momentary emissions that were eliminated from regression analysis.

CONCLUSION

Our results showed that peat compaction lowers the soil surface level and thus reduces the relative water table depth. However, the compaction did not change physiochemical properties in either ecosystem. Further, this study was able to determine a strong relationship between water table depth and emissions which can be used for modelling future emissions, especially at SF sites. As such, more work is required to unpick the effect of compaction from that of water table depth.

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